

Oxidation of Hydrazine with Acid Permanganate and Dichromate. Part II

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WITH respect to oxidation of hydrazine, permanganate and dichromate have been described as complex deelectronators¹, which may oxidise hydrazine through a sequence of 1- and 2-equivalent steps represented by

The diimide radicals formed (iii) condense into isotetrazene to decompose ultimately into N_2H and NH_3 ². With acid permanganate Browne and Shetterly³ found little N_2H as a product in the oxidation of hydrazine, a small percentage being formed only in hot concentrated sulphuric acid medium. Hought, Sherk and Browne⁴, on the other hand, found that the reaction was non-stoichiometric involving both (i) and (ii).

With dichromate, early workers⁵⁻⁹ assumed nitrogen to be the only oxidation product, but Cuy and Bray¹⁰ demonstrated later that the oxidations involve several side reactions but "in the limit" correspond to complete oxidation of hydrazine to nitrogen. Tanatar¹¹ obtained hydrogen azide among the products with both acid permanganate and dichromate though not quantitatively.

To the best of our knowledge, no further work regarding the stoichiometric behaviours of these oxidations have been reported and the present work was taken up to ascertain the exact course of events in these oxidations.

Experimental

Solutions of potassium permanganate (A.R.) and potassium dichromate (S.Merck) were prepared and standardised by usual methods^{12,13}. The stock solution of hydrazine sulphate (B.D.H.) was standardised by iodate method¹⁴. The experimental details of potentiometric methods have been reported earlier¹⁵ by us and the results are summarised in the tables and graphs.

Results and Discussions

When permanganate is gradually added to hydrazine inflexion occurs at 0.33 moles (sulphuric acid concentration 0.5*N* to 4*N*), 0.4 moles (sulphuric

acid concentrations 8*N*) and 0.53 moles (sulphuric acid concentrations 18*N*) of permanganate per mole hydrazine. These results can not be explained in terms of simple stoichiometric equations. It may be assumed that one- and two-equivalent steps (i, ii

TABLE 1. 0.04051 (*M*) KMnO_4 ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.00931 (*M*) HYDRAZINE SULPHATE TEMP. 30°; REACTION MIXTURES STORED FOR 72 HR

H_2SO_4 concentrations (approx.)	Points of inflexions (in ml. of KMnO_4)	Moles of KMnO_4 per mole of hydrazine
0.5 <i>N</i>	0.77	0.33
1 <i>N</i>	0.77	0.33
2 <i>N</i>	0.77	0.33
3 <i>N</i>	0.77	0.33
4 <i>N</i>	0.77	0.33
8 <i>N</i>	0.92	0.40
18 <i>N</i>	1.25	0.53

TABLE 2. 0.0931 (*M*) HYDRAZINE SULPHATE ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.002025 (*M*) POTASSIUM PERMANGANATE SOLN. TEMP. 30°; REACTION MIXTURES STORED FOR 72 HR.

H_2SO_4 concentrations (approx.)	Points of inflexions (in ml. of hydrazine)	Moles of N_2H_4 per mole of KMnO_4
0.01 <i>N</i>	0.5	2.0
1 <i>N</i>	0.5	2.0
2 <i>N</i>	0.5	2.0
3 <i>N</i>	0.5	2.0
4 <i>N</i>	0.5	2.0
8 <i>N</i>	0.5	2.0

TABLE 3. 0.016 (*M*) DICHROMATE SOLN. ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.0025 (*M*) HYDRAZINE SOLUTION, TEMP. 30°; REACTION MIXTURES STORED FOR 72 HR.

H_2SO_4 concentrations (approx.)	Points of inflexions (in ml. of dichromate)	Moles of dichromate per mole of N_2H_4
0.2 <i>N</i>	1.0	0.66
1 <i>N</i>	1.0	0.66
2 <i>N</i>	1.0	0.66
4 <i>N</i>	1.0	0.66

and iii) do not assert themselves to equal extents and the predominance of one over the other changes with mineral acid concentrations. At concentrations > 4*N* the overall reaction is

in which ammonia is formed simultaneously through steps (iii) and (i). At acid concentration > 4*N*, the oxidation proceeds exclusively through step (iii),

NOTES

and at very high concentration of sulphuric acid (18*N*) through steps (ii) and (iii), both of which are two electron transfer steps. The net reaction in the latter case then corresponds to

In the reverse case, when hydrazine is added to permanganate, hydrazoic acid with a very high oxidation potential ($E^\circ = 3 \cdot 09$)¹⁶ stands little chance of being formed as long as permanganate is in excess and the single inflexion that occurs at 2.0 moles hydrazine per mole permanganate is consistent with the single one-equivalent oxidation step (i) leading to the formation of nitrogen and ammonia.

TABLE 4. 0.0937 (*M*) HYDRAZINE SOLUTION ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.0016 (*M*) DICHROMATE SOLUTION, TEMP. 30°; REACTION MIXTURES STORED FOR 72 HR.

H ₂ SO ₄ concentrations (approx.)	Point of inflexions (in ml. of N ₂ H ₄)	Moles of hydrazine per mole of dichromate
0.2 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4
1 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4
2 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4
3 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4
4 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4
6 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4
8 <i>N</i>	0.4	2.4

When dichromate is gradually added to hydrazine, single inflexion occurs at 0.66 moles of dichromate per mole of hydrazine in all cases (0.2*N* to 8*N* sulphuric acid media). This means that the oxidation proceeds exclusively through two equivalent steps of the type (ii).

The stoichiometry does not change with changes in either reactant concentrations or mineral acid concentrations. In view of these, this reaction may be considered to be analytically significant.

In the reverse case, inflexion occurs at 2.4 moles of hydrazine per mole of dichromate consistent with the equation,

indicating that the reaction proceeds more through two equivalent steps of the type (ii) than through (i).

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A Convenient Method for Chlorination of Ketones

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THE chlorination of ketones to date^{1,2,3} involves the preparation first of hypochlorite compound or the passage of chlorine gas separately generated into the solution of the compound. Both of these procedures are more time consuming and inconvenient. We were interested in the preparation of the chloro derivatives of the compound I_a and I_b, C.D. studies of which prompted us to look for a convenient method for the chlorination.

Compound I_a or I_b when dissolved in acetic acid and to which almost double the molar quantities of HCl and H₂O₂ were added at 5°-10°, gave after work up almost 80-85% of the yield of the 6-chloro derivatives (I_c & I_d). The elemental analysis and N.M.R. spectrum support the structures I_c & I_d. N.M.R. spectra in addition to the reported pattern of the compounds⁴ shows two doublets (1 proton each) centred at 5.75 δ and 2.45 δ with a coupling constant of 7 cps. This would be in agreement with the trans coupling⁵ of the two hydrogen at C₅ & C₆. Further I_c & I_d on treatment with zinc dust and acetic acid gives the corresponding amines I_e & I_f, the structures of which were confirmed by their I.R.